

TENSILE PROPERTIES AND FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF BIAXIAL WEFT KNITTED COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

Knitted composites possess attractive properties for niche applications, such as those requiring high energy absorption or good impact resistance, or in cases where the component is complex in shape and demands exceptional formability [1]. To increase mechanical properties, weft knitted fabrics could be reinforced with warp and weft threads. These types of reinforcements are called biaxial weft knitted structures. Within the design of our experiments, it was compared the effect of aramid and glass yarn as a stitch yarn in the biaxial weft knitted composite. After production of one layer composites, tensile properties of them had been investigated both in experimental and finite element analysis (FEA). It was found that composites with glass stitch yarn exhibits higher tensile properties in the course and wale directions than composite with aramid stitch yarn. The very good agreement between the experimentally determined tensile modules and finite element method calculation supports the applicability of FEM for biaxial weft knitted composites.

2 Introduction

In recent years, knitted reinforcements for composites have gained more attention due to their unique properties. Knitted fabrics are constructed by loops which can extend easily and slide which generates a higher degree of deformability in comparison with other types of reinforcements. Knitted fabrics are basically categorized into two types, namely warp knitted fabrics and weft knitted fabrics. Warp knitted fabrics are produced by knitting in the lengthwise direction (wale direction) of the fabrics. Weft knitted fabrics are produced by knitting in the horizontal direction (course direction) of the fabrics. Weft knitted fabrics offer great

possibilities of near-net-shape structures, by this way manual work can be reduced [2]. There are two kinds of loops in the weft knitted fabrics. One is needle loop and another one is sinker loop (figure 3) [3]. Biaxial weft knitted fabrics include weft and warp yarn layers, which are held together by a stitching yarn system. Reinforcing yarns, e.g. glass or aramid fibres, can be used within all yarn systems. They provide necessary strength and stiffness of the fabric [4]. The present work concentrates on the tensile properties and FEM of biaxial weft knitting composites. Mainly the effect of stitch yarn type was investigated. The FEM consists of several steps: a) building the model of geometry of the knitted structure, b) refinement of this geometry under consideration of the mechanical properties of the yarns and resin, c) modelling of the mechanical or other behavior of the structure [5]. In the literature, contributions about the modelling of knitted composites were reported, however limited study has been made about the modelling of biaxial weft knitted composites.

3 Experimental Procedures

3.1 Preparation of the Composites

520 tex E-glass yarn (Nippon Electric Glass Co. Ltd.) was used as reinforcement material. 68 tex E-Glass (ECG 75 1/1 OZ, Hokuriku Fiber-Glass Co. Ltd.) and 28/2 Ne Aramid were used as stitch yarns. Vinyl ester resin (Ripoxy R-806, Showa High Polymer Co. Ltd) was used as matrix. Biaxial weft knitted fabrics were produced on a flat bed knitting machine (Shima Seiki Mfg., Ltd). Warp yarn density in both of the specimen was 2 end/cm. Weft yarn density in the specimen with glass stitch yarn was 4.6 end/cm and this in the specimen with aramid stitch yarn was 6.3 end/cm. Composite panels with

one ply preform were fabricated by hand lay-up method. Spacers were used to control the required specimen thickness. The composite panels were cured at room temperature for 24 h, followed by a 2-h post-cure at 100 °C. The notation GF-GF-AR means that in the order warp yarn is GF (glass fiber), weft yarn is GF (glass fiber) and stitch yarn is AR (aramid fiber). GF-GF-GF composites had about 0.7 mm overall panel thickness and 26.7 % overall fiber volume fraction. GF-GF-AR composites had about 0.9 mm overall thickness and 29.2 % overall fiber volume fraction.

3.2 Mechanical Characterization

Tensile tests were conducted according to ASTM-D303 standard; under constant displacement rate 1 mm/min (Universal testing machine Type 55R4206, Instron). Finite element analysis was executed on a personal computer by using the MARC software.

3.3 Finite-element Model

The tensile modules of the GF-GF-GF and the GF-GF-AR composites were calculated by FEM analysis (E_{FEM}). Four different modellings were performed: a) The GF-GF-AR in the wale direction b) The GF-GF-AR in the course direction c) The GF-GF-GF in the wale direction d) The GF-GF-GF in the course direction.

The FE modellings include repeating unit cell structure in the biaxial weft knitted composite. The straight yarn in warp (vertical) and weft (horizontal) directions, the loop yarns and resin were modeled as depicted in figure 3. Figure 4 demonstrates the actual structure of the composite after consolidation. Finite element analysis was executed by 3D beam elements. The all modellings consist of 6886 elements and 2520 nodes.

3.3.1 Geometric Properties

The internal structures of warp, weft and stitch fiber bundle elements are presented in table 1. Geometric properties of fiber bundle elements were calculated by using values of internal structure. In both laminas, the area of warp fiber bundle elements (glass fiber) was higher about 1.5 times than the area of weft fiber bundle elements (glass fiber). The area of aramid stitch fiber bundle elements was almost 2 times higher than the area of glass stitch fiber bundle elements. The width and thickness of fiber bundle elements of modellings were figured out by using

aspect ratio. The aspect ratio can be calculated by proportion of major and minor axis of cross-section of fiber bundle. Moments of inertia of the fiber elements were calculated by using width and thickness of fiber bundle elements.

3.3.2 Material Properties

The value of material constants of each fiber bundle element is shown in table 2. The resin was involved in the fiber element. Fiber volume fraction of fiber elements was calculated by observation of cross-section. To figure out volume fraction of fibers, the area of fiber bundle, from observation, was divided the area of fiber bundle from catalogue value. Young's modules of fiber elements were calculated by equations of law and mixture (1).

$$E_L = E_f \times V_f + E_m \times (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

where E is Young's modules and V_f is fiber volume fraction [4]. Table 3 exhibits input values for the calculation of young's modules of fiber bundle elements.

3.3.3 Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions were given to carry out calculation under tensile load. In the wale direction of modellings of both composites, the longitudinal displacements of the nodes on the CD were fixed, and the incremental displacement was given to the nodes on the AB. The nonlinear analysis method was performed by incremental displacement of the nodes on AB at each step 0.05 mm. In the course direction of modellings of both composites, the longitudinal displacements of the nodes on the AC were fixed, and the incremental displacement (0.05 mm) was given to the nodes on the BD (figure 3).

4 Results and Discussions

In order to get a high comparability, volume fractions of the two types of specimens were kept constant. Due to the higher volume element of the aramid stitch yarn, final composite thickness was higher. The results of tensile modules from experiments (E_{exp}) and FEM (E_{FEM}) are demonstrated in table 4. In all specimens, E_{FEM} was very close to the experimentally determined tensile modulus values (E_{exp}), respectively.

The GF-GF-GF composites exhibit higher tensile properties in the course and wale directions than the GF-GF-AR composites. The tensile modules of both specimens, in the course direction, were higher than those of both specimens in the wale direction. This was caused by the different warp and weft yarn density in knitting fabric.

The woven and braided fabrics have crimp on the reinforcement yarns in the thickness direction which affects the mechanical properties. On the other hand, knitted fabrics have an orientation of yarns not only in the thickness but also in the fabric plane. Therefore the orientation of the yarns is more complex in comparison with woven and braided fabrics. Strength of the samples both in course and wale directions are given in table 5. Samples with glass fiber stitch yarns give higher strength values in both directions. Better interfacial characteristic of glass stitch yarns were seemed the main cause of this difference.

5 Conclusions

This study showed that the biaxial GF-GF-GF composites had higher tensile properties (modulus and strength) in the course and the wale directions than the GF-GF-AR composites. A better interfacial bonding of glass stitch yarn was caused of this result. All composites had higher strength and modules values in the course direction compared to the wale direction. This was caused by the different warp and weft yarn density in knitting fabric. Finite element modelling can be used to estimate the tensile modulus values of the composites with a very good agreement. In all specimens, E_{FEM} was very close to the experimentally determined tensile modulus values (E_{exp}).

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Fig. 1. Photographs of biaxial weft knitted reinforcement fabrics, (a) GF-GF-GF, (b) GF-GF-AR

Fig. 2. (a) Schematic drawing of tensile test, (b) Apparatus for tensile test

Fig.3. Finite element model of biaxial weft knitted composite (GF-GF-AR)

Fig.4. Modelled composite structure of biaxial weft knitted reinforcement (GF-GF-AR)

Table 1 Internal structure of warp, weft and stitch yarns

GF-GF-AR and GF-GF-GF	Major axis (mm)	Minor axis (mm)	Aspect ratio (Major axis / Minor axis)	Area (mm ²)
Warp (GF)	2.43	0.31	7.82	0.48
Weft (GF)	1.67	0.26	6.34	0.33
Stitch (GF)	0.55	0.35	1.57	0.15
Stitch (AR)	0.84	0.54	1.55	0.29

Table 2 Material constants of each fiber bundle element

GF-GF-AR and GF-GF-GF	Fiber volume fraction (%)	Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio
Warp (GF)	42	39714	0.25
Weft (GF)	61	56187	0.23
Stitch (AR)	5	7385	0.35
Stitch (GF)	18	19166	0.28

Table 3 Input values for the calculation of young's modulus of fiber bundle elements

	E _L (GPa)	E _T (GPa)	v _L
Glass fiber bundle	90	90	0.22
Aramid fiber bundle	85	2.59	0.3
Matrix	3.3	0.33	0.3

Table 4 The results of tensile test and FEM

Sample	Modules from Experiment E _{exp} [GPa]	Modules from FEM E _{FEM} [GPa]	Difference between E _{FEM} and E _{exp} [%]
GF-GF-GF (C)	14.8±0.43	14.81	2.75
GF-GF-AR (C)	13.6	13.32	2.1
GF-GF-GF (W)	11±0.3	10.95	3.1
GF-GF-AR (W)	8.9	8.66	2.69

Table 5 Strength of specimens

Samples	Range	Strength (MPa)
GF-GF-GF (C)	1	239.2± 14.6
GF-GF-AR (C)	2	185.7 ± 23.7
<u>GF-GF-GF (W)</u>	1	119.8 ±3.9
<u>GF-GF-AR (W)</u>	2	94.9 ±13

(C= Course, W= Wale. Testing directions were showed by underline; e.g. GF)

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